

The factors Affect Long Term Debt Structure in Industrial Firms

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to investigate the factors that affect the long term debt structure in industrial firms. The data was collected through Amman Stock Exchange Market for the period 2000-2010. Non parametric regression was used to measure the effect. The results showed that there is effect of adverse effect of profitability, while there is positive effect of fixed assets, and firm age. On the other hand, there was not effect for the growth and non-debt tax of the firm.

Keywords: Long Term Debt, Industrial Firms

Introduction

The survival of business activities depends mainly on the financing activities. There are three methods for financing business activities. These methods are: cash surplus from operations, equity and borrowing from banks and non-banks using short term debt to finance working capital requirements and long term debts to finance capital expansion, fixed assets etc. Non-banks are mainly investors in capital market (Mazhar and Nasar, 2005).

Since mid-sixties, capital structure is considered as a widely open subject attributed to some observable and non-observable constructs and variables, in order to pinpoint and set-up the various determinations and implications (indicators/proxies) on such capital structure for industries and firms. However, these variables use leverage measures variety of proxies as dependent variables such as long term debt divided by firm value, the debt to assets ratio (book value) and total liabilities to total assets as leverage.

Commonly, leverage can be defined as the ratio of the mean level of long term debt, in respect to some other independent variables. Multicollinearity can be considered in capital structure studies to play a significant role in measuring the impact of capital structure. In essence, the relationship between the capital structure and its determinants can be represented as cause-and-effect relationship, in view of the fact that the determinants are the cause that affect the capital structure, which can be formulated comprehensively as two sides construct that encompass the whole frame works. Consequently,

the framework specifies the casual relation amongst the two constructs, the casual relation for the determinants can be long term debt, short term debt, and deflated debt.

Furthermore, this causality leads to conduct a critical investigation on organizational factors in which these determinants have several indicators such as growth, firm size, assets, profitability, non-tax shields, industry, and uniqueness. On the other hand these determinants can give an indication for instance the R&D to total assets and gives an indication of growth.

Nevertheless, the essential business decisions' on firms is based on the capital structure. On the other hand the cost of capital is considered as a key factor in balancing the mixture of debt and equity; used to finance the firm operation. Most firms employ several types of capital, stated as capital components, with common and preferred stocks, as well as debt. Accordingly differences in risk and securities imply different required rates of returns, and the cost of capital should be a weighted average of the various components' costs which is called weighted average cost of capital or WACC (Brigham and Ehrhardt, 2005).Furthermore,the ratio of the mix of funds depends on the firm and known as optimal capital structure of the firm, which is explained by the different capital structures theories in how it can increase the value of the firm and its impact on its cost of capital.

Companies working in this sector are depending on equity for financing their investments in relation to

their total finance. In addition, growing companies and companies with high levels of tangible assets tend to use short term debt more frequently compared to large and profitable companies which tend to use less debt overall. Moreover the industrial sector in Jordan should be clarified and analyzed depending on the capital structure theories (Khreish and Khrawesh, 2008).

Literature

Several studies have discussed this subject to determine capital structure and long term loans of Jordanian listed mining and extraction industries, based on the trade-off theories, in order to achieve the optimal capital structure based on the marginal value of the benefits associated with the debt (Al-Quddah, 2011); The determinants of capital structure of Jordanian mining and extraction industries: Empirical evidence). Moreover, this study used the panel data analysis tool, along with empirical analysis.

As a result, the empirical study identified the relation nature between the profitability and leverage. The study proved that Jordanian firms tend to have much, by inspecting the relation and impact between the capital structure determinants all the way through fixed effects model in which, the model conclude the relation and effect of Capital Structure of Jordanian Mining and Extraction Industries.

Caglayan (2011) aimed to investigate the determinants of capital structure of Turkish firms and focuses on the differences between firms in different quintiles of the debt-capital distributions by using Quintile Regression. As a result, the study reached to identify the factor explaining the firms' decisions with respect to their financial leverage, by analyzing measures for the debt ratio, along with long term and short term debts separately, in order to determine the differences of empirical implication of capital theories for different types of debts. Thus, it also analyzes the tangibility, profitability, and growth to examine the relation with the capital structure. Accordingly, tangibility was found to have a negative relation to long term debts, with positive relation regarding both the short and total debt ratios. However, based on the static trade-off and agency cost theories, the size of firm is an essential variable for the ratio of long term

debt, internally it generates funds and prohibits it from turning to external. These findings are consistent with previous empirical studies for developing countries. Nevertheless, the results demonstrate the relation between profitability effects on all debt ratios to be stated as negative impact. Moreover, the study demonstrate the usage financing of retained profit and debt as the firm will count primarily on the retained profit to cover their needs in addition to external debt for additional requirements, as they put forward that firms prefer to use retained profits in financing their needs and use debt only when additional fundamentals are required. This finding confirms the pecking order theory. Consequently, the growth was found to have positive impact on debt ratios, in which firms will need more debt in order to invest more.

To determine the capital structure of listed firms in sugar and allied industry in Jordan, Awan et al., (2011) conducted a study on 33 firms in the sugar and allied sector, listed at Karachi Stock Exchange for the period 1999-2004. The data was analyzed using pooled regression in a panel data analysis. The study found out that a specific industry capital structure, exhibits unique attributes, which are usually not apparent in the combined analysis, in many sectors, by utilizing the balance sheet analysis of joint stock companies listed in the Karachi Stock Exchange volume II. Based on the panel analysis and regression model the result approved the impacts of determinants on the capital structure in sugar and allied industry.

Another study examined the capital structure of listed industrial companies on Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) over the period (2001-2005), (Khreish and Khrawesh, 2008; evidence from Jordanian industrial companies), which aimed to contribute towards a better understanding of financing behavior in Jordanian industrial companies, in order to conclude The primary objective of capital structure decisions, maximize the Market value of the firm using long term sources with appropriate mix. The study reached to Growing companies and companies with high levels of tangible assets tend to use short-term debt instead of long-term debt. However the study attempts to reduce the gap, by analyzing a capital structure since Jordan differs from other developing, as it has a financial market that has been ranked as one of the

best among the emerging markets ,according to Standard and Poor (S&P) Indexes.

Song (2005) aimed to analyze the explanatory power of some of the theories proposed to explain variations in capital structures across firms. Particularly, this study Investigating capital structure determinants of Swedish firms based on a panel data set from 1992 to 2000 comprising of about 6000 companies. The study reached to confirm that most of the determinants of capital structure suggested by capital structure theories are relevant with Swedish firms. But it also found significant differences in the determinants of long and short-term forms of debt. As a result, applying panel data analysis, may lead to reveal possible correlations between the long term and short term leverage among firm financial systems, firm debt structure, and growth

Buferna, *et al.*(2005) aimed to provide evidences of the capital structure and long term theories pertaining to a developing country, and examine the impact of the lack of a secondary capital market, by analyzing a capital structure question with reference to the Libyan business environment. Cross-sectional OLS regression analysis results for trade-off theory and the agency cost theory are compatible for the structure of Libyan companies, while the evidence was little to support the asymmetric information theory. The lack of a secondary market impacted the agency costs. The study reached to that, both the static trade-off theory and the agency cost theory are pertinent theories to the Libyan companies, which will give a better understanding of financing behavior in Libyan companies. On the other hand it is likely that equity agency costs, arising, due to conflict between debt holders and shareholders, will be more of a problem for private companies and indeed the relationships supporting the agency cost theory, were stronger for private companies.

Mazhar and Naser (2005) examined the factors affect the capital structure in Pakistani Government owned and private firms they found that government owned and private companies of Pakistan use different patterns of financing, and that government owned companies, pay more leverage than private companies. Nevertheless conducting this study, will minimize the gap between the actual analysis of these countries and other studies based on significant data and will give a critical analysis

on these countries capital structure, according to their economic indications.

Methodology

The problem of this research can be perceived by answering the following questions:

Is there a statistical significance impact between firm characteristics and long term debt structure?

- Is there a statistical significance impact between firm size and long term debt?
- Is there a statistical significance impact between firm age and long term debt?
- Is there a statistical significance impact between growth and long term debt?
- Is there a statistical significance impact between profitability and long term debt?
- Is there a statistical significance impact between non-debt tax shield and long term debt?
- Is there a statistical significance impact between tangibility and long term debt?

The components of the study represent all the listed industrial firms in Jordan, taken from Amman Stock Exchange Market site on the internet. The sample is all the industrial public companies in Jordan that represent 113 companies, which will be selected in the sample of the study, in order to be able to cover all the variables of the study with high degree of accuracy in the presence of such a small population. After reviewing the content of the subject of the research, the researcher will be analyzing the financial information about the firms in the sample selected provided in Amman Stock Exchange website, as a major method for data collection. This guarantees measuring all the variables identified in the research including the independent and dependent variables.

The data will be collected from the supplemental information, provided by Amman Stock Exchange Market website, related to the industrial public companies using their financial statements and other records of the sample selected from 2000 to 2010.

The research objectives are expected to be achieved by analyzing the financial information about the industrial firms selected in the sample of study and calculating the ratios previously identified. The

relationships between the independent and dependent variables identified in the hypotheses of study will be examined later by studying a panel data regression analysis to be performed. Panel data is a combination of cross section and time series data. A panel data approach is more valuable than either cross-section or time-series data

Alone. There are many benefits of using panel data: of which is controlling individual heterogeneity; gives more useful data, more variability, less co linearity among the variables in addition to more degrees of freedom and efficiency.

Results

The results in Table (1) show the effect of profitability on firm long term debt. The effect was negative indicating that increasing profitability will decrease long term debt. There is no statistical significance impact between fixed assets tangibility and firm long term debt.

Table 1: The impact of profitability on firm long term debt

Component	B value	Standard error	Wald value	Sig.
Constant	-1.055	0.715	2.179	0.140
Profitability	-0.304	0.087	12.196	0.001
Cox and Snell R ²	0.004			
Nagelkerke R ²	0.005			

The results in Table 2 indicate that there is effect of fixed assets tangibility on long term debt. The results showed that increased the fixed assets will decrease the long term debt.

Table 2: The impact of fixed assets tangibility on firm long term debt

Component	B value	Standard error	Wald value	Sig.
Constant	-1.047	0.191	54.132	0.001
Fixed assets	2.608	0.411	40.256	0.001
Cox and Snell R ²	0.070			
Nagelkerke R ²	0.094			

There is no statistical significance impact between non-debt tax shield and firm long term debt. There is any effect of non-debt tax on long term debt. The Wald value for hypothesis testing was 0.506 and significance was 0.477 which is more than ($\alpha=0.05$).

Table 3: The impact of non-debt tax on firm long term debt

Component	B value	Standard error	Wald value	Sig.
Constant	-0.422	0.138	9.328	0.002
Non-debt tax	2.164	3.041	0.506	0.477
Cox and Snell R ²	0.001			
Nagelkerke R ²	0.001			

Table 4 shows that there is no statistical significance impact between growth and firm long term debt. There is any effect of growth on long term debt. The Wald value for hypothesis testing was 2.358 and significance was 0.125 which is more than ($\alpha=0.05$).

Table 4: The impact of growth on firm long term debt

Component	B value	Standard error	Wald value	Sig.
Constant	-0.379	0.086	19.226	0.0001
Growth	0.731	0.476	2.358	0.125
Cox and Snell R ²	0.004			
Nagelkerke R ²	0.005			

Table 5 shows there is no statistical significance impact between firm age and long term debt. The results showed the effect of firm age on long term debt. The results showed that with increasing the age of firm, the long term debt will decrease with significant effect ($\alpha < 0.05$).

Table 5: The impact of firm age on firm long term debt

Component	B value	Standard error	Wald value	Sig.
Constant	1.326	0.383	12.005	0.001
Firms' age	-0.574	0.129	19.745	0.001
Cox and Snell R ²	0.034			
Nagelkerke R ²	0.045			

Discussion

Size is found to have statistically significant and positive impact on the firm's leverage in the study of Rajan and Zingale (G-7) countries, Shah and Hijazi (KSE companies) and Abubakar Saeed energy sector. This suggests that larger firms in Jordan tend to have higher leverage ratios and large firms borrow more than smaller firms. This result is consistent with the implementation of static trade-off theory, which suggests that for obtaining the optimal capital structure if firm needs a change in the capital structure. Further, larger listed firms in industrial sector

of Jordan have state ownership (partial or complete state controlled) that facilitates them with less chance of bankruptcy and easy access to bank debts. As result high cost of bankruptcy is not a big threat for state-owned firms in Jordan to have high leverage level. The most of empirical studies that include the data from developing countries find a positive relation between size and financial leverage. For instance: Titman and Wessels [25], Rajan and Zingales [5] and Booth et al [10] provide the evidence of significant direct relationship between size and financial leverage. Larger Companies use more debt rather than equity to raise their financing.

Whereas it shows negative trend in the study of Industrial Sector of has negative relation with leverage. The negative sign indicate the evidence

about the negative relationship of size and leverage. The value of size is not statistically significant even on 10%. Based on this insignificant result I am not in a position to confirm that there is a negative relationship between size and leverage. We may conclude that results of size prove the static trade-off and Agency cost theory.

5.2 Conclusion

The data used in this study has been taken from the "Balance Sheet Analysis of Joint Stock Companies listed in the Amman Stock Exchange which is published by the State Bank of Jordan and Balance Sheet Analysis of Joint Stock Companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange available on the web site www.ase.com.jo. We used pool regression model of panel data analysis. According to this, we have measured the determinants of capital structure in the listed Industrial Jordanian firms of from 2005 to 2010. This study analyzed a sample of 97 firms in the industrial sector by using a pooled regression model to measure the determinants of capital structure of the firms in the industrial sector. In the analysis, we have found the effect of size, profitability, tangibility, and growth (all are independent variables) on the leverage (dependent variables) position of the company. With the help of regression, we have found that size and profitability have the negative relationship and tangibility and growth have the positive relationship with the leverage. However, the results for size and growth

are not statistically significant. According to this we are not in a position to conclude that size and growth have the negative or positive relationship with leverage due to their insignificant results so we reject our hypothesis related with the size and growth. Profitability shows the negative sign and it is statistically significant so it may be concluded that the profitability and leverage are negatively related with each other in the case of listed Industrial firms of Jordan and my hypothesis is also correct about the profitability. Tangibility is positively related with leverage and it is also statistically significant so hypothesis regarding tangibility is accepted and concludes that there is positive relationship between tangibility and leverage of the listed Industrial firms of Jordan.

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